

Baltic Sea Production Centre BALTICSEA_REANALYSIS_PHY_003_011

Issue: 2.5

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CHANGE RECORD

When the quality of the products changes, the QUID is updated and a row is added to this table. The third column specifies which sections or sub-sections have been updated. The fourth column should mention the version of the product to which the change applies.

Issue	Date	§	Description of Change	Author	Validated By
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2.0	12 th April 2019	All	Update of document: Including data for 2017 Including rerun of period: 2012-2016	S. Jandt	
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I EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

I.1 Products covered by this document

The product BALTICSEA_REANALYSIS_PHYS_003_011 is a Baltic Sea physical reanalysis for the period January 1993-December 2018 at 3.9 km resolution. Hence, the reanalysis product covers 25 whole years. The product was calculated with the coupled physical-biogeochemical model system NEMO-SCOBI.

This reanalysis product was extended with data for the year 2018 for the CMEMS product Catalogue release in December 2019. However, the quality information of the product in this report covers only the simulation period 1993-2017.

I.2 Summary of the results

The quality of the present BAL physical reanalysis, which covers the period January 1993 to December 2017, has been assessed by comparison with both dependent and independent observations. The results for the BAL physical reanalysis are summarized below.

Sea levels:

In general, the results for the Baltic Sea are good, with mean correlations of about 0.95 and mean RMS deviation of about 7 cm. In the Danish Straits the mean correlation was weaker, about 0.84, and the mean RMS deviation was about 12 cm. In the Kattegat-Skagerrak area the mean correlation was about 0.88, and the RMS deviation was about 11 cm, i.e. slightly better than in the Danish Straits but not as good as in the Baltic Sea.

Sea ice:

Correlations of Baltic Sea ice extent were about 0.90, compared to independent observations. Meanwhile, the ice volume is satisfying for most of the investigated years except for 2016, which overestimated the ice volume, indicating too thick ice.

Salinity:

According to innovation statistics (dependent observations) for the whole domain, the mean bias of the product, which includes data assimilation, was less than about 0.1 ppt and the remaining RMS deviation was less than about 0.6 ppt. The corresponding deviations using independent data, i.e. data not used for assimilation, were more than -0.55 ppt in the Kattegat and less than 0.15 ppt in the Baltic proper. The RMSD was less than 4.1 ppt in the Kattegat and less than 0.6 ppt in the Baltic proper, respectively (largest values in the Danish Straits).

Temperature:

According to innovation statistics (dependent observations) for the whole domain, the mean bias of the product, which includes data assimilation, was less than about 0.1 °C and the remaining RMS deviation was less than about 0.7 °C. The corresponding deviations using independent data are between -0.4 and 0.15°C. The RMSD at independent stations is between 0.4 and 1 °C, respectively (largest values in the Kattegat and the Gulf of Finland).

Important notice: During the course of this reanalysis, the atmospheric forcing used has been changed. We used Euro4M atmosphere reanalysis (22 km HIRLAM) for the simulation period up to the end of 2011 and continued the simulation using UERRA reanalysis (11 km) from 2012 onwards.

I.3 Estimated Accuracy Numbers

Table 1. Estimated Accuracy Numbers

Variable	Unit	Mean RMSD
Sea levels (Baltic Sea / Danish Straits / Kattegat-Skagerrak)	m	0.07 / 0.12 / 0.11
Sea ice extent	km ²	20,000
Sea ice volume	km ³	15,000
Salinity, dependent data, 0-5 m (forecast / analysis)	ppt	1.1 / 0.6
Salinity, dependent data, 5-30 m (forecast / analysis)	ppt	1.0 / 0.4
Salinity, dependent data, 30-80 m (forecast / analysis)	ppt	0.7 / 0.3
Salinity, dependent data, 80-220 m (forecast / analysis)	ppt	0.4 / 0.3
Salinity, independent data, 0-5 m	ppt	1.1
Salinity, independent data, 5-30 m	ppt	0.9
Salinity, independent data, 30-80 m	ppt	0.6
Temperature, dependent data, 0-5 m (forecast / analysis)	°C	0.9 / 0.5
Temperature, dependent data, 5-30 m (forecast / analysis)	°C	1.0 / 0.7
Temperature, dependent data, 30-80 m (forecast / analysis)	°C	1.0 / 0.7
Temperature, dependent data, 80-220 m (forecast / analysis)	°C	0.6 / 0.5
Temperature, independent data, 0-5 m	°C	0.9
Temperature, independent data, 5-30 m	°C	1.2
Temperature, independent data, 30-80 m	°C	1.1

II PRODUCTION SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

Production centre name: Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute (SMHI)

Production subsystem name: Baltic Sea physical reanalysis (CMEMS name: BALTICSEA_REANALYSIS_PHYS_003_011)

Description

The circulation model used in the reanalysis is NEMO-Nordic (Hordoir et al., 2015; Pemberton et al., 2017), based on NEMO (Nucleus for European Modelling of the Ocean) version 3.6 coupled to the sea ice model LIM (Louvain-la-Neuve Sea Ice Model), also version 3.6. NEMO-Nordic has been the operational ocean and sea ice model used at SMHI since 2016. In this reanalysis, NEMO-Nordic is one-way coupled to the biogeochemical model SCOBI (Swedish Coastal and Ocean Biogeochemical model). As it is only one-way coupled, the physics (NEMO-Nordic) will affect the biogeochemistry (SCOBI) but not the other way round. The domain of the setup covers the North Sea as well as the Baltic Sea; see Figure 1.

Figure 1. Map of the North-Sea Baltic Sea area showing the model domain.

At the lateral boundary in the western English Channel and along the Scotland-Norway boundary, the sea levels are prescribed using a coarse (44 km resolution) storm-surge model called NOAMOD (North

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Atlantic Model). Climatological monthly mean values of salinity and temperature are used at the boundary, and it is assumed there is no sea ice. Further, 11 tidal constituents are added for sea levels at the boundary, and a radiation condition is applied for velocities.

The turbulence model is a state-of-the-art buoyancy-extended k-epsilon model. The ice model LIM-3.6 is two-way coupled with NEMO-3.6. A biogeochemical model called SCOBI (Swedish Coastal and Ocean Biogeochemical model) is currently only one-way coupled to NEMO-Nordic. Thus, it does not affect the physical component in the current setup.

The river runoff is specified as daily means from the output of the hydrological model E-HYPE, running operationally at SMHI. The number of rivers is of the order of a few hundred along the coastline.

The meteorological forcing is from HIRLAM (High-Resolution Limited Area Model) with 22 km resolution, from project Euro4M (Dahlgren et al., 2014) and covers the most of the reanalysis period, 1993-2011. From 2012 onwards, the meteorological forcing is from the UERRA reanalysis product (European Regional analysis) with 11km resolution.

The data assimilation method chosen for this reanalysis is Localized Singular Evolutive Interpolated Kalman (LSEIK) filter, which uses an ensemble of model states; see Nerger et al. (2005). It is a multivariate method, which means many variables are potentially affected by each observation. The model uncertainty is specified using an ensemble of model states, which implies that the Background Error Covariances are inhomogeneous and non-isotropic.

The variables assimilated are SST charts from the Swedish Ice Service at SMHI as well as in-situ measurements of T/S (Temperature and Salinity) profiles from the ICES data base (<http://www.ices.dk>).

The forecasting system is run with 72-hour cycling, which implies a new forecast of 72 hours is made every 72 hours, using the best weather forcing. See Figure 2.

Figure 2. Schematic showing the forecasting cycle.

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Compared to the older Baltic reanalysis product BALTICSEA_REANALYSIS_PHYS_003_008 (V201704), the present reanalysis product uses a different circulation model and a different ice model. Further, the present product has higher horizontal resolution, approximately 3.9 km compared to 5.6 km in V201704. Also, the vertical resolution is slightly higher near the surface, about 3 m compared to 4 m in V201704. The lateral boundary conditions are very similar, the river runoff is identical, and the meteorological forcing is almost identical. The present product includes the calendar year 2017, which the old product did not. Finally, the present product is coupled to a biogeochemical model, but that does not affect the physical part of the system described in this document.

This reanalysis product will be extended in time as soon as enough forcing data (meteorological forcing fields and in-situ observations) are available for the reanalysis production. The plan for the time extension for this product is:

From Spring 2020 a new upgrade procedure for all CMEMS Reanalysis products will start:

- Monthly interim extensions will be produced as soon as the first necessary data are available for an initial interim reanalysis production.
- Later final productions (re-calculations) will be performed when more data have become available for the production. This final production is scheduled to take place twice annually:
 - The final production of the first half of year 2019 is scheduled to be released in July 2020
 - The final production of the second half of year 2019 is scheduled to be released in December 2020
 - And so on...

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III VALIDATION FRAMEWORK

The product variables assessed here are sea level, sea ice, salinity and temperature. For salinity and temperature, four pre-selected standard depth intervals have been selected for analysis: 0-5 m, 5-30 m, 30-80 m, and 80-500 m. These depth intervals are used when summarizing innovation statistics, i.e. statistics of observations minus model values for observations used in the data assimilation. In addition, independent near-surface and near-bottom observations are used in the validation of salinity and temperature. For sea levels, error statistics were calculated using data from sea level gauges that were not used in data assimilation. Finally, ice was validated using independent data of the integrated quantity ice extent, and dependent data were used to validate short forecasts and analyses in observation points.

The types of observational data used in the validation are summarized in the table below.

Table 2. Overview of observational data used in the validation.

Variable	Data source
Sea level	CMEMS sea level stations (not used in DA)
Ice extent and volume	CMEMS ice charts from FMI and SMHI (not used in DA)
Salinity	ICES data (used in DA)
	Buoy data and CTD data (not used in DA)
Temperature	ICES (used in DA)
	Buoy data and CTD data (not used in DA)
	CMEMS L4 SST product (not used in DA)

IV VALIDATION RESULTS

IV.1 Sea level

The sea level quality is assessed by comparing hourly instantaneous model data with corresponding coastal observations (see Figure 3). It was decided to analyse one sample year for this: 2015. Apart from the sample year, annual mean RMS deviations were calculated for the whole time period for each sea level station using available observations. The details can be found in the Sea Level Appendix (see references). The tide gauge stations used in the validation are shown in Figure 3 below.

Figure 3. Map showing the coastal sea level stations used in the validation.

Summary of the results for sea level

The results of the analysis were calculated for three different sample years: 1995, 2005 and 2015 (the last is included in the figures in the Sea Level Appendix, see references), and for three different regions: the Baltic Sea, the Danish Straits and the Kattegat-Skagerrak. For the early year 1995, at Kattegat-Skagerrak area the correlation for sea level was around 0.91 slightly decreasing to around 0.89 in the Danish Straits, and increasing to around 0.96 in the Baltic Sea. The corresponding RMS deviations were around 9.4 cm, 10 cm and 6.5 cm, respectively. The year 2005 year did not showed improvement compared to 1995, with correlations decreasing to around 0.87 in the Kattegat-Skagerrak and Danish Straits and with correlation around 0.96 in the Baltic areas. The corresponding RMS deviation increases in the Kattegat-Skagerrak area and in the Danish Straits to around 11.2 and 10.6 cm, respectively. In the Baltic Sea, the corresponding RMS deviations decreased to around 6.3 cm in 2005. For the third sample year, 2015, we see slightly worse results in the Danish Straits area compared to 2005 and 1995. The RMSD increased to 12.6 cm and correlation was 0.83. In the Baltic Sea in 2015, the results have improved: RMS deviation decreased to 5.6 cm and the correlation was high around 0.95. In the Kattegat-Skagerrak area correlation slightly decreased to 0.84 and RMSD was not much higher than in 1995 around 9.7 cm, but less than in 2005. However, an inter-annual variation can be expected due to different weather situations. The results are summarized in Table 3 below.

Table 3. Summary of results for sea levels (based on the three years 1995, 2005, 2015).

	Mean correlation	Mean RMS deviation
Baltic Sea	0.96	6 cm
Danish Straits	0.86	11 cm
Kattegat-Skagerrak	0.87	10 cm

IV.2 Sea ice

Baltic Sea Ice Extent

Sea ice extent can be calculated from all gridded ice concentration data, both observations and model data. It is defined as the summed area of all grid cells that have at least 15 % ice cover. Figure 4 shows the ice extent from observations from SMHI ice chart as well as the V201704 and V201907 reanalyses. Comparing the two reanalyses, we see that they both give good results in terms of ice extent, where sometimes V201704 is best and sometimes V201907 is best.

Figure 4. Baltic ice extent according to observations (black dots), the former reanalysis version (V201704; red line) and the present reanalysis version (V201907; green line).

Ice concentration climatology

Ice concentration maps were created by calculating the monthly mean ice concentration for each grid cell of the product, based on the whole 24-year time series. The result for January to May is shown in Figure 5 panels (a) to (e) below, and December in panel (f). According to the climatology, the months June to November are virtually ice free and are therefore left out.

Figure 5. Monthly climatology of sea ice concentration for the months (a) January, (b) February, (c) March, (d) April, (e) May, and (f) December. All other months have no ice or very little ice.

Taylor diagrams for ice extent and ice volume for the period 2011 to 2017

The Baltic Sea ice extent in the REA V201907 product was also validated using independent ice observation data from FMI ice charts. Figures 6-7 show the results for the time periods 2011-2017. The validation is done by (1) visual comparison of time series and (2) error statistics in terms of a Taylor diagram (standard deviation, centred RMS deviation, and correlation. The results indicate that the result is satisfying, even though no data assimilation was done for sea ice.

Figure 6. Time series of ice extent for 2011-2017 (top) and error statistics in terms of a Taylor diagram (bottom).

Figure 7. Time series of ice volume for 2011-2017 (top) and error statistics in terms of a Taylor diagram (bottom).

Further, the total ice volume in the REA product was compared with the ice volume according to the FMI ice charts, using visual inspection, as well as error statistics in terms of a Taylor diagram. This is done in Figure 7, which indicates that the analysed ice volume is often very well described in the REA V201907 product, except in the last ice season 20105/2016. For this year the ice extent compares well with observations, indicating that the ice thickness must be overestimated during this ice season compared to the FMI data.

Summary of the results for sea ice

The ice cover has been validated against observations of sea ice extent. The result is very satisfying for V201907. This is also the case for sea ice volume, except for the last ice season, early 2016 (and possibly other years not investigated here), where the ice volume is overestimated.

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IV.3 Salinity

The quality of the salinity is assessed by comparing the modelled salinity with all available observations from stations. The available salinity stations used in the validation are shown in Figure 13 below. More details can be found in the Salinity Appendix (see references).

In this reanalysis, the data assimilation process is done every 3 days. Before the forecast, the observations have been used to reduce the bias in the initial condition for the forecast. Therefore, every DA cycle equals to a 72-hour forecast with a corrected initial condition. From the innovation statistics, the analysis biases are largely reduced by DA relative to the forecast bias. Therefore, the DA setup in this Baltic reanalysis can constrain the forecast bias of the coupled physical-biogeochemical modelling.

We haven't done any other bias correction like nudging to climatology.

Innovation statistics as time series

Monthly mean bias and RMS deviations were calculated for the reanalysis product for the time period 1993-2016. Statistics is calculated both before the data assimilation ("Forecast") and after ("Analysis"). Figures 8–11 show the result for four pre-selected standard depth intervals as time series with monthly resolution.

In the surface layer (0-5m; Figure 8), the forecast and the analysis both have rather small bias deviations, usually much smaller than 0.5 ppt, and a mean which is slightly positive. The RMS deviation for the analysis is around 0.6 ppt as a mean for the reanalysis period. The forecast deviations are slightly higher, often slightly above 1 ppt during the reanalysis period.

In the second layer (5-30m; Figure 9), the bias deviations of the forecasts have become slightly negative, sometimes reaching -0.2 to -0.4 ppt whereas the bias of the analysis is closer to zero. The RMS deviations have decreased somewhat compared to the surface layer.

In the third layer (30-80m; Figure 10), the forecast bias deviations have switched sign as predominantly positive but usually smaller than 0.2 ppt. The analysis bias deviations are very close to zero. The corresponding RMS deviations have also decreased compared to the second layer, the forecast deviations being around 0.7 ppt and the analysis deviations around 0.3 ppt.

In the deepest layer (80-220 m; Figure 11), bias deviations are for the most time very small, typically reaching +/-0.1 ppt. This is also seen in the RMS deviation, which are small for most of the time, around 0.3 ppt except the second year which shows slightly larger deviations.

Figure 8. Mean bias (top) and RMS deviation (bottom) for the layer 0-5m, for the reanalysis. Unit: ppt.

Figure 9. Mean bias (top) and RMS deviation (bottom) for the layer 5-30m, for the reanalysis. Unit: ppt.

Figure 10. Mean bias (top) and RMS deviation (bottom) for the layer 30-80m, for the reanalysis. Unit: ppt.

Figure 11. Mean bias (top) and RMS deviation (bottom) for the layer 80-220m, for the reanalysis. Unit: ppt.

Innovation statistics as vertical profiles

The innovation statistics were also used to calculate mean vertical profiles of error statistics, again using dependent observations. Figure 12 shows the result for the time period 1993-2017. Again, red lines are for statistics calculated for the reanalysis *before* the data assimilation (“Forecast”), and blue curves are for the reanalysis *after* the data assimilation (“Analysis”). It is clear that the analysis has smaller RMS deviations compared to the forecast at all levels, whereas the mean bias in the first and last levels is actually slightly larger in the analyses.

Figure 12. Mean statistics of observation – model for salinity, in the four standard layers 0-5 m, 5-30 m, 30-80 m, and 80-220 m. The observations are dependent and the time period is 1993-2016. Red lines denote results for the V201907 REA product before assimilation (the forecast) and blue lines denote the V201907 REA product after assimilation (the analysis).

Error statistics using independent observations

In the above, the error statistics were calculated using innovation data from the data assimilation system, i.e. observations that were included in the data assimilation. However, as buoy data were not included in the data assimilation, we could use these as independent observations. In addition, as only bottle data were used in the data assimilation, CTD data from monitoring stations are also independent. The map in Figure 13 shows the locations of these buoys and monitoring stations. Figure 14 shows error statistics for the uppermost levels of all stations, and Figure 15 for the deepest levels. See the Salinity Appendix for more details (see references).

Figure 13: Positions of all salinity stations validated. Permanent stations are coloured blue and monitoring stations with CTD observations are coloured red.

Figure 14. The lowest layer of each salinity offshore station: Bias, cRMSD (equivalent with standard deviation of error), correlation and the percentage of missing observations (right plot, black markers).

Figure 15. The deepest layer of each salinity offshore station: Bias, cRMSD (equivalent with standard deviation of error), correlation and the percentage of missing observations (right plot, black markers).

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Summary of the results for salinity

According to the innovation statistics for the whole domain, the mean bias of the product, which includes data assimilation, is slightly positive near the surface, about 0.1 ppt. Further down in the water column the remaining bias deviation is even lower. The corresponding RMS deviations are largest near the surface, about 0.5-0.6 ppt, but decreasing to about 0.3 in the deeper layers.

Using independent data, the mean bias is about -0.17 ppt in the surface layer, -0.03 ppt in the depth layer between 5 and 30 m, and 0.22 in the depth layer between 30 and 80m. The corresponding RMS deviations using independent data are 0.8 ppt near the surface and 1.1 ppt near the bottom.

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IV.4 Temperature

The quality of the temperature is assessed by comparing the modelled temperature with all available observations from stations. The available 14 temperature stations used in the validation are shown in Figure 21 below.

In this reanalysis, the data assimilation process is done every 3 days. Before the forecast, the observations have been used to reduce the bias in the initial condition for the forecast. Therefore, every DA cycle equals to a 72-hour forecast with a corrected initial condition. From the innovation statistics, the analysis biases are largely reduced by DA relative to the forecast bias. Therefore, the DA setup in this Baltic reanalysis can constrain the forecast bias of the coupled physical-biogeochemical modelling.

We haven't done any other bias correction like nudging to climatology.

Furthermore the surface temperature is validated with L4 satellite data.

More details can be found in the Temperature Appendix (see references).

Innovation statistics as time series

Just as in the case of salinity, monthly mean bias and RMS deviations is calculated for the reanalysis run for the time period 1993-2016. Statistics were calculated both before the data assimilation ("Forecast") and after the data assimilation ("Analysis"). Figures 16-19 show the result for the four pre-selected standard depth intervals.

In the surface layer (0-5m; Figure 16), the reanalysis (both the forecasts and the analyses) has a seasonally varying bias which is negative in the summer, with analysis biases sometimes reaching -0.5°C. The corresponding RMS deviations are slightly higher, about 0.6°C.

In the second and third layers (5-30 m and 30-80 m, respectively; Figure 17-18), the bias deviations have increased somewhat compared to the surface, and the seasonal variation is still present in the second layer, also in the analysis. The RMS deviations have also increased somewhat compared to the surface, with maxima during the summer seasons.

In the fourth layer (80-220 m), the bias and RMS deviations decrease to much lower values compared to the upper layers. See Figure 19.

Figure 16. Mean bias (top) and RMS deviation (bottom) for the layer 0-5m, for the reanalysis. Unit: °C.

Figure 17. Mean bias (top) and RMS deviation (bottom) for the layer 5-30m, for the reanalysis. Unit: °C.

Figure 18. Mean bias (top) and RMS deviation (bottom) for the layer 30-80m, for the reanalysis. Unit: °C.

Figure 19. Mean bias (top) and RMS deviation (bottom) for the layer 80-500m, for the reanalysis. Unit: °C.

Innovation statistics as vertical profiles

As in the case of salinity, we may also calculate mean vertical profiles of innovation statistics for the time period 1993 - 2017. The left panel of Figure 20 shows that mean bias deviation of the reanalysis (forecasts and analyses) are really close to zero, reaching a maximum in the 30-80 m depth interval and then decreasing to near zero again in the deeper layers.

The right panel of Figure 20 shows that both the analysis and forecast RMS deviations both peak in the 30-80 m interval, with the analysis deviation being about 0.7 °C, before decreasing again in the lowest layers, to less than 0.5 for the analysis.

Figure 20. Mean statistics of observation – model for temperature, in the four standard layers 0-5m, 5-30m, 30-80m, and 80-220 m. The observations are dependent and the time period is 1993-2016. Red markers denote before assimilation (the forecast) and blue markers denote after assimilation (the analysis).

Error statistics using independent observations

In the above, the error statistics were calculated using innovation data from the data assimilation system, i.e. observations that were included in the data assimilation. However (just as in the case of salinity), as buoy data were not included in the data assimilation, we could use these as independent observations. In addition, as only bottle data were used in the data assimilation, CTD data from monitoring stations are also independent. The map in Figure 21 shows the locations of these buoys and monitoring stations. Figure 22 shows error statistics for the uppermost levels of all stations, and Figure 23 for the deepest levels. See the Temperature Appendix for more details (see references).

Figure 21: Positions of all temperature stations validated. Permanent stations are coloured blue and monitoring stations with CTD observations are coloured red.

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Figure 22: Error statistics from independent temperature data at the lowest available depth at each station.

Figure 23: Error statistics from independent temperature data at the deepest available layer of each station.

Summary of the results for temperature

According to the innovation statistics for the whole domain, the mean bias of the product, which includes data assimilation, reaches a maximum of +0.08 °C in the 30-80 m depth range, whereas in the other depth ranges the bias is less than 0.05 °C as a mean. The RMS deviation also reaches a maximum in the 30-80 m depth range, with a mean of about 0.7 °C. The other levels have smaller deviations, e.g. about 0.6 °C in the surface layer.

Using independent observations from surface buoys and CTD casts, the mean bias is -0.09° C in the surface layer, -0.02°C in the layer between 5 – 30m and +0.14° C in the layer 30 – 80 m. The mean RMS deviation in the surface layer is 0.7 °C and 0.8 °C near the bottom.

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V QUALITY CHANGES SINCE PREVIOUS VERSION

The current version of the reanalysis is a complete rerun compared to the latest version (Product id: BALTICSEA_REANALYSIS_PHYS_003_008 (V201704)). The circulation model is now NEMO-Nordic, whereas in V201704 it was HIROMB. The data assimilation system is now LSEIK whereas in V201704 it was 3D EnVar. The resolution of the model has increased from about 5.6 km in V201704 to about 3.9 km in V201907. However, the meteorological forcing, river runoff and lateral boundary conditions were identical or very similar in V3 compared to V201907. Another difference is the length of the reanalysis: V201704 covers 1989-2015 and V201907 covers 1993-2016. In addition, with so many changes there are inevitably changes to the quality, in some cases to the better and in some cases to the worse:

- Sea levels: Improved quality in the Baltic Sea whereas the quality in the Danish Straits were slightly worse or similar
- Sea ice: The absence of sea ice data assimilation in V201907 led to slightly lower quality in ice extent and ice thickness compared to V201704
- Temperature: Mixed results; improvements in some places compared to V201704
- Salinity: Mixed results; improvements in some places compared to V201704
- Currents: not validated in V201907

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VI REFERENCES

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All appendixes of this Quid (CMEMS-BAL-QUID-003-011, (2019)) are available at.

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